

Geophysical Research Letters[®]

RESEARCH LETTER

10.1029/2021GL096335

Key Points:

- We present observations of the four MMS spacecraft crossing Earth's bow shock seemingly in the reverse order
- The observations, supported by an ion-kinetic simulation, reveal that short-large amplitude magnetic structures cause the shock to reform
- These multispacecraft signatures can be used in the future to identify shock reformation

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Correspondence to:

A. Johlander,
andreasj@irfu.se

Citation:

Johlander, A., Battarbee, M., Turc, L., Ganse, U., Pfau-Kempf, Y., Grandin, M., et al. (2022). Quasi-parallel shock reformation seen by Magnetospheric Multiscale and ion-kinetic simulations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *49*, e2021GL096335. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL096335>

Received 28 SEP 2021

Accepted 8 JAN 2022

© 2022. The Authors.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Quasi-Parallel Shock Reformation Seen by Magnetospheric Multiscale and Ion-Kinetic Simulations

Andreas Johlander^{1,2}

¹Swedish Institute of Space Physics, Uppsala, Sweden, ²Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland,

³Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

Abstract Shock waves in collisionless plasmas are among the most efficient particle accelerators in space. Shock reformation is a process important to plasma heating and acceleration, but direct observations of reformation at quasi-parallel shocks have been lacking. Here, we investigate Earth's quasi-parallel bow shock with observations by the four Magnetospheric Multiscale spacecraft. The multi-spacecraft observations provide evidence of short large-amplitude magnetic structures (SLAMS) causing reformation of the quasi-parallel shock. We perform an ion-kinetic Vlasiator simulation of the bow shock and show that SLAMS reforming the bow shock recreates the multi-spacecraft measurements. This provides a method for identifying shock reformation in the future.

Plain Language Summary A shock wave forms when a supersonic flow encounters an obstacle. Shock waves can even form in the ionized plasma that inhabits most of the seemingly empty space in our solar system, galaxy, and the rest of the universe. One such a shock is found in front of Earth as the fast stream of plasma flowing from the Sun, known as the solar wind, encounters Earth's magnetic field. Under certain conditions, shock waves can become unsteady and evolve in time. Specifically, it is thought that a new shock can form in front of and replace the old shock in a process known as shock reformation. This process is important for how shock waves heat the plasma and can play a major role in how shocks accelerate particles. In this work, we use data from satellites that fly through Earth's shock and compare to a computer simulation of the shock wave. We find that a type of magnetic pulsation in front of the shock wave causes it to reform. The method of finding this reformation process presented here can also be used in the future to find shock reformation.

1. Introduction

Collisionless shock waves are some of the most energetic phenomena in astrophysical plasmas. Shock waves form around planets, stars, galaxies, and supernova remnants where they are responsible for the generation of galactic cosmic rays through diffusive shock acceleration (e.g., Abdo et al., 2010; Bell, 1978). A characteristic feature of shocks is their ability to reflect a portion of the incoming ions back into the upstream plasma. The angle θ_{Bn} between the shock normal and the upstream magnetic field then determines the structure of the shock. In quasi-perpendicular shocks, where $\theta_{\text{Bn}} \gtrsim 45^\circ$, reflected ions are turned around by the upstream magnetic field (Sckopke et al., 1983) and the shock appears as a sharp transition between upstream and downstream. If the shock instead is quasi-parallel with $\theta_{\text{Bn}} \lesssim 45^\circ$, reflected ions travel upstream, exciting waves and turbulence and forming the foreshock. This causes the quasi-parallel shock transition to be more extended and dynamic (Schwartz & Burgess, 1991).

Early observations (Greenstadt, 1985) from Earth's bow shock and simulations (Burgess, 1989; Thomas et al., 1990) found that the quasi-parallel shock can be nonstationary, meaning that the structure of the shock changes periodically in time. An important type of structure in the quasi-parallel shock are upstream shock-like pulsations known as short large-amplitude magnetic structures (SLAMS; Schwartz & Burgess, 1991). SLAMS propagate against the flow in the plasma frame but are advected toward the shock (Schwartz et al., 1992) and they are thought to form from ultra-low frequency (ULF) waves (Thomsen et al., 1988). Proposed formation mechanisms for SLAMS involve buildup of energetic ion pressure on the downstream edge of the SLAMS (Giacalone

Figure 1. MMS1 observations of a quasi-parallel shock crossing. (a) Magnetic field in GSE. (b) Ion number density. (c) Ion bulk velocity in GSE. (d) Omnidirectional ion phase-space density as a function of energy.

($\theta_{\text{Bn}} \sim 50^\circ$) crossing from when MMS was in a string-of-pearls formation and showed that upstream ULF waves in the foreshock cause a cyclical reformation of the shock. They also found that ion reflection is modulated by the reformation and that the remnants of the old shock ramps could be observed in the downstream. Despite these recent advancements, it is still not clear how reformation manifests itself in quasi-parallel shocks and how upstream waves and pulsations interact with the shock.

In this article, we present direct observational evidence of SLAMS participating in quasi-parallel shock reformation. We use multipoint observational data from the MMS satellites during a crossing of Earth's bow shock. We further demonstrate, using a global hybrid-Vlasov simulation, how shock reformation by SLAMS recreates the observed multi-spacecraft signatures.

2. Observations

We use data from the four MMS spacecraft (Burch et al., 2016). Magnetic field data are from the fluxgate magnetometer (Russell et al., 2016) which collects the magnetic field vector with a cadence of 128 Hz. Since the full resolution data from MMS4 are not available at this time, we use the survey mode data which are collected with a cadence of 8 Hz for this spacecraft. The ion data are from the fast plasma investigation dual ion spectrometer (Pollock et al., 2016) instrument, which measures the ion distributions and moments every 150 ms. To avoid sampling the disturbances in the immediate upstream foreshock region, we obtain the asymptotic upstream field and plasma values from the Wind spacecraft (Lepping et al., 1995; Ogilvie et al., 1995), situated upstream of Earth. The Wind data, time-shifted to the bow shock, are obtained from the OMNI database (King & Papitashvili, 2005).

Figure 1 shows a series of quasi-parallel shock crossings by MMS1 on 13 January 2019 around 22:21 UTC. The spacecraft were on the outward leg of their orbit, positioned at $\sim(11, -3, 5)R_E$ in Geocentric Solar Ecliptic (GSE) coordinates, where $R_E = 6371.2$ km is the Earth radius. MMS was in a tetrahedron formation with spacecraft separation of ~ 32 km and the solar wind was characterized by a relatively slow speed and high number density, see Table 1. MMS start out in the downstream magnetosheath plasma and the shock motion causes the spacecraft to cross to the upstream foreshock, evident by the presence of the cold solar wind beam around 22:21:00 in Figure 1d. The bow shock motion then reverses to the sunward direction and overtakes the spacecraft orbital motion (Maksimovic et al., 2003), leading them to cross back to the downstream plasma in an extended crossing marked with gray in Figure 1. During this crossing, MMS observe a number of large compressions of the magnetic field magnitude B and ion number density N_i , indicating the presence of SLAMS. The B -amplitude of

et al., 1993) and a nonresonant instability (Bell, 2004) of the ULF waves with backstreaming ions (Chen et al., 2021). While Earth's quasi-parallel bow shock has been described as a wide patchwork of SLAMS (Schwartz & Burgess, 1991), simulations often show a less extended transition where SLAMS form closer to the shock and participate in the cyclical reformation of the shock (e.g., Burgess, 1995; Caprioli et al., 2015; Hao et al., 2017; Scholer et al., 2003; Tsubouchi & Lembège, 2004). Simulations by Scholer (1993) showed that quasi-parallel reformation is dominated by SLAMS that steepen ~ 20 inertial lengths upstream of the shock. Using observations from the four Cluster satellites, Lucek et al. (2008) found that SLAMS inhabit a rather narrow region (few thousand kilometers) upstream of the shock. SLAMS have long been considered to be important for the variability and reformation of quasi-parallel shocks, but direct observations have so far been lacking.

There has been recent advancement on shock reformation with the high-cadence measurements from the Magnetospheric Multiscale (MMS) spacecraft. Yang et al. (2020) found evidence of shock reformation of the quasi-perpendicular bow shock and Turner et al. (2021) found evidence for ion-kinetic scale reformation of a shock upstream of a hot flow anomaly. Madanian et al. (2021) investigated a quasi-perpendicular high-Mach number shock ($M_A \sim 27$) with periodic behavior, similar to those observed at Saturn's bow shock (Sulaiman et al., 2015), and found signatures of both shock rippling (Winske & Quest, 1988) and reformation. Liu et al. (2021) used an oblique

Table 1
Upstream and Shock Parameters at the Spacecraft Location in the MMS Observations and in the Vlasiator Simulation

Parameter	Observations	Simulation
Upstream number density N_u	22 cm ⁻³	1 cm ⁻³
Bulk speed V_u	300 km s ⁻¹	750 km s ⁻¹
Magnetic field \mathbf{B}_u	(3.7,-2.8,1.6) nT	(-2.99,0.26,0) nT
Shock normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$	(0.96,-0.15,0.22)	(0.97,0.24)
Shock angle θ_{Bn}	~30°	19°
Alfvén Mach number M_A	13	11
Fast mode Mach M_f	8	9
Upstream ion $\beta_{i,u}$	0.5	1.9
Ion inertial length $d_{i,u}$	48 km	230 km
Ion gyroperiod $T_{ci,u}$	13 s	22 s
SLAMS leading edge speed	100 km s ⁻¹	380 km s ⁻¹

Note. Vector quantities are in GSE coordinates.

the SLAMS increases as MMS gets closer to the shock and proceed into the downstream, consistent with previous observations (Lucek et al., 2008). From the large-amplitude compressive structures, we conclude that the spacecraft stay relatively close to the bow shock. However, it is evident from the large density compression and significantly heated solar wind that the spacecraft is located in a shocked downstream plasma. The spacecraft then return to the upstream foreshock around 22:22:10.

An important parameter for our analysis is the angle θ_{Bn} between the upstream magnetic field \mathbf{B}_u and the shock normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$. To determine $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, we use the bow shock model by Farris et al. (1991) fitted to the position of MMS (Schwartz, 1998). We find that the shock Alfvén Mach number is 13 and θ_{Bn} is around 30°, which means this is a quasi-parallel shock. We validate the upstream solar wind measurements from Wind with local values obtained by MMS in the foreshock after 22:22:10 and find a good match between the measurements. There is still some uncertainty in θ_{Bn} because of the uncertainty of the time-shift of the solar wind and because the bow shock itself can have large-scale rippling causing $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ to fluctuate and θ_{Bn} to change during the event (Hao et al., 2016, 2017).

Figure 2 shows the relative positions of the four spacecraft and a zoomed-in interval of the shock crossing. To more clearly visualize the ion distribution function, we show the reduced ion phase-space density F_i as a function of velocity along $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ in Figure 2d. We see that there is a relatively clear distinction between times where MMS1 observes the cold solar wind beam, that may be decelerated, and where this beam is heated and compressed significantly. We note, however, that both these types of plasmas are in the extended shock transition region.

Figure 2c shows that the first sharp increase in B is advected downstream across the spacecraft and that MMS1 returns to the upstream where it again observes the cold solar wind beam. Since this structure reaches a value of $B/B_u \sim 8$, we conclude that this is a SLAMS situated upstream of the bow shock. We see that there is a reflected ion population with $v_n \gtrsim 0$ just before the SLAMS (also reported by Chen et al. (2021)). Since the SLAMS is moving antisunward in the spacecraft frame, these reflected ions are antisunward of the SLAMS and moving toward it. The same type of reflected ion population is seen after the SLAMS and before the next structure. The

second sharp increase in B appears slightly different to the first SLAMS since MMS1 does not observe the cold solar wind beam again directly after the encounter. Instead, the spacecraft observes heated and compressed plasma even after the peak in B . This increase in B can appear at first glance to be the shock ramp proper that MMS crosses from the upstream to downstream. But, as we shall see, this is not the case.

Figure 2c shows that the first spacecraft to observe the increase in B is MMS2, followed by MMS1, MMS3, and finally MMS4. This is the reverse order of what would be expected of an upstream-to-downstream shock crossing since, as we see in Figures 2a and 2b, MMS2 is the spacecraft positioned furthest upstream and the other spacecraft are further downstream. So, while the overall shock motion is directed upstream, the motion of this structure is directed downstream. This means that what appears to be the shock crossing is, in fact, a SLAMS that is merging with the shock. Throughout the event in Figure 2, there is no conventional shock crossing where the shock simply moves along $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ over the four spacecraft. Instead a train of SLAMS merges with the bow shock, causing the shock to jump forward, leading to the spacecraft ending up in the heated and compressed downstream plasma.

To quantify the motion of the merging SLAMS, we perform a four-spacecraft timing analysis. We find the time delays by minimizing the mean square deviation of B in the shaded area in Figure 2c. From this, we find that the

Figure 2. Four-spacecraft observation of the shock transition from the shaded interval in Figures 1 (a) and 1(b) Spacecraft positions relative to the tetrahedron center in the GSE x - y and x - z planes. The shock orientation and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ before the shock crossing are shown. (c) B observed by the four spacecraft. (d) Reduced ion distribution as a function of v_n observed by MMS1.

Figure 3. Vlasov simulation of Earth's bow shock. (a) Part of the simulation showing N_i . (b)–(d) Zoomed-in snapshots in the simulation at different times. The three virtual spacecraft are shown as colored dots. Black (blue) contour line shows where B (N_i) is two times the upstream value.

velocity of the leading edge of the structure is 100 km s^{-1} and the direction of propagation is $(-0.64, -0.05, -0.76)$, which is 140° from \hat{n} . Slightly different B -profiles seen by the spacecraft indicate non-planarity or evolution of the structure. Error analysis (Vogt et al., 2011) shows that the uncertainty in propagation speed is $\sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and the uncertainty in direction is $\sim 15^\circ$. This means that the structure is moving with a small angle toward the shock with a speed significantly lower than the solar wind, meaning that the structure is propagating against the flow in the plasma frame. We find that the trailing edge moves downstream at $\sim 34 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, meaning that the SLAMS has slowed down as it merged with the shock. The timing analysis confirms that what appears to be a shock crossing is instead the downstream edge of a SLAMS impacting the shock.

3. Simulation

To validate and to investigate the scales of the SLAMS reformation process, we perform a two-dimensional simulation of the bow shock with the global hybrid-Vlasov code Vlasiator (Palmroth et al., 2018; von Althaus et al., 2014). In the simulation, ions are described as distribution functions which are propagated with the Vlasov equation and electrons are modeled as an adiabatic charge-neutralizing fluid. The electric field is closed by the generalized Ohm's law $\mathbf{E} = -\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{B} + (\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_e)/N_i q_e$ where \mathbf{j} is the current density, q_e is the elementary charge, and \mathbf{P}_e is the electron pressure tensor, using isotropic and adiabatic electron heating. The simulation provides a global view of the quasi-parallel bow shock and allows us to investigate scales not achievable with the small spacecraft separation of MMS.

The simulation box is in the GSE X - Y plane with $X \in [-8, 72]R_E$ and $Y \in [-32, 32]R_E$ with a grid resolution of 300 km and a velocity grid resolution of 30 km s^{-1} . The inner boundary at $5R_E$ is a nearly perfect conductor. The solar wind flows from the upstream edge in the negative X -direction. The upstream solar wind conditions of the simulation can be seen in Table 1. Figure 3a shows a part of the simulation box at the time $t = 378 \text{ s}$ where we see the curved, quasi-parallel, bow shock as an increase in N_i . See the Supporting Information for an animation of a part of the simulation.

We would like to preface the simulation analysis with discussion on the solar wind parameters in Table 1. First, the relatively fast solar wind speed is used so that fewer computational resources are spent while the bow shock initializes. Second, the relatively low solar wind density of 1 cm^{-3} and magnetic field of 3 nT are set in part to approximately match the observed M_A and in part to keep $d_{i,u}$ comparable to the grid resolution. The local shock parameters that determine most of the relevant physics at the shock are similar to those observed during the shock crossing by MMS. However, $\beta_{i,u}$ is higher in the simulation because the uniform velocity grid resolution requires a certain temperature to resolve the solar wind well without increasing the computational cost of the remaining velocity domain excessively.

Several SLAMS-like structures form and merge with the shock during the simulation. The timescales on which SLAMS are seen here are slower than in Figure 2, likely due to the greater ion gyroperiod in the simulation. We can see an example of a SLAMS just upstream of the bow shock at $X \sim 10R_E$ and $Y \sim 4R_E$ in Figure 3a, marked with a black box. To obtain \hat{n} of the shock at the position of the SLAMS, we use a fourth-order polynomial fit to where $N_i = 2N_u$ (Battarbee et al., 2020) and determine the normal to that curve. The resulting \hat{n} and the shock parameters are shown in Table 1. The parameters $M_A = 11$ and $\theta_{Bn} = 19^\circ$ are similar to those observed by MMS, despite the different solar wind conditions.

To better interpret the MMS multipoint measurements, we insert three *virtual spacecraft* into the simulation. The virtual spacecraft sample the field and plasma parameters to create time series that mimic spacecraft observations. The large scale bow shock motion is naturally directed sunward due to the two-dimensional simulation setup and constant solar wind conditions. The spacecraft are positioned in an equilateral triangle centered around

Figure 4. Multipoint virtual spacecraft observations in the Vlasior simulation. (a) B (b) N_i . (c) Omnidirectional ion phase-space density. (d) Reduced ion distribution as a function of v_n .

a simulation cell where the ion distribution function is saved. The plasma quantities are interpolated to the position of the virtual spacecraft. The inter-spacecraft distance is ~ 520 km which corresponds to $2.3d_{i,u}$.

Figures 3b–3d show three snapshots of N_i at the bow shock in the simulation with the virtual spacecraft (denoted VS1-3) positions indicated. At $t = 371$ s, there is a magnetic structure visible upstream of the spacecraft. This structure is $\sim 1R_E$ ($\sim 30d_{i,u}$) upstream of the shock surface and has enhanced B and N_i above two times their upstream values. The spatial extent of the structure is on the order of $\sim 1,000$ km normal to the shock and $\sim 1R_E$ perpendicular to the shock. At $t = 378$ s, this structure has further grown in amplitude and has a maximum value of B more than four times the upstream value. This structure is therefore similar to the SLAMS observed by MMS. At $t = 385$ s, the SLAMS has encountered the shock, causing it to jump forward over the spacecraft, which are now positioned downstream of the shock. The spacecraft later cross back to the upstream at $t \sim 420$ s similar to MMS in the previous section. At the same time, another SLAMS is forming upstream of the spacecraft, see the supporting animation.

Next, we look at the time series “measurementsE” made by the virtual spacecraft, shown in Figure 4. The spacecraft start out downstream of the shock and then cross to the upstream at $t \sim 368$ s. The spacecraft then observe the cold solar wind beam and a reflected ion population simultaneously at ~ 375 s, similar to the MMS observations, see Figure 2d. The spacecraft then

observe the SLAMS as a peak in B with $B/B_u \sim 6$. Like in the observations, the spacecraft continue to observe heated and compressed plasma even after the SLAMS has merged with the shock, as can be seen in Figures 4c and 4d. We note that the trailing edge of the SLAMS, seen in the downstream plasma, is less pronounced than in the MMS observations. However, we see in the supporting animation after ~ 392 s that there is a compressive structure moving antisunward in the magnetosheath, making the exact downstream signatures sensitive to where the virtual spacecraft are placed.

Despite only observing one SLAMS, the multi-spacecraft time series in the simulation show the same signature as the MMS observations at the shock transition. We see in Figure 4a that VS2, which is the spacecraft furthest upstream (see Figures 3b–3d), observes the increase in B first, followed by VS1 and then VS3. This shows that, while the overall shock motion is directed upstream, reformation by a SLAMS leads to the same reverse order in B as in the MMS observations. We perform a timing analysis of this structure, which is applicable using three spacecraft instead of four because of the two-dimensional geometry of the simulation. Using the measured B in the gray interval in Figure 4a, we find that the structure is propagating with 380 km s^{-1} along $(-1.00, 0.07)$ which is 160° away from \hat{n} . This means that like in the observations, the structure is moving with a small angle toward the shock and is propagating against the flow in the plasma frame. These observations confirm that a SLAMS which is impacting the shock, causing it to reform, does result in the multipoint observational signatures seen by MMS.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we report the first direct evidence of SLAMS participating in the shock reformation process of a quasi-parallel shock. We analyze one crossing of Earth's bow shock by the four MMS spacecraft where a number of SLAMS are observed. We find that the transition from upstream to downstream takes place in the antisunward direction, indicating that a SLAMS is impacting the bow shock, causing it to reform. We demonstrate this process by inserting three virtual spacecraft into a hybrid-Vlasov bow shock simulation. In the simulation, we observe a SLAMS forming $\sim 30d_{i,u}$ upstream of the shock and later impacting the shock. During this process, the virtual spacecraft record the same multi-spacecraft signatures during the shock crossing, thus showing that this reformation process recreates the MMS observations. We propose that the combination of what, in single spacecraft observations, looks like an upstream-to-downstream shock crossing, but with the multi-spacecraft observations in the reverse order, is a clear sign of reformation and can be used in the future to identify these events.

These findings advance our understanding of the cyclical nature of collisionless shocks. Liu et al. (2021) found that periodic changes in the upstream conditions due to ULF waves can modulate the oblique shock and cause it to reform. In this work, we observe reformation at a moderately high-Mach number quasi-parallel shock. Under these conditions, the observations and simulation show that shock-like SLAMS form in the upstream and merge with the shock, causing reformation. The simulation shows that the SLAMS and the shock coexist for some time before reformation, similar to recent observations of the quasi-perpendicular bow shock (Madanian et al., 2021). The MMS observations and the simulation also indicate that SLAMS form rather close to the shock, in agreement with findings by Lucek et al. (2008) and that SLAMS are an integral part of the reformation process at quasi-parallel shocks. Future studies should focus on the role of the shock reformation in particle heating and energization at quasi-parallel shocks.

Data Availability Statement

The MMS data are available through the MMS Science Data Center <https://lasp.colorado.edu/mms/sdc/public/>, and the CDA Web <https://cdaweb.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/index.html>. The OMNI data are available from the GSFC/SPDF OMNIWeb interface <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov>. Vlasiator (Pfau-Kempf et al., 2021) is distributed under the GPL-2 open-source license. The run described here take several terabytes of disk space and are kept in storage maintained within the CSC-IT Center for Science. Vlasiator data presented in this paper can be accessed by following the data policy <https://www2.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/vlasiator/rules-of-the-road>.

Acknowledgments

This research was made possible with the data and efforts of the people of the MMS mission. The authors wish to thank the Finnish Grid and Cloud Infrastructure (FGCI) and specifically the University of Helsinki computing services for supporting this project with computational and data storage resources. Andreas Johlander is grateful to ISSI, Bern, and Working Team 454. We acknowledge the European Research Council Starting grant 200141-QuESpace, with which Vlasiator was developed, and Consolidator grant 682068-PRETISSIMO awarded to further develop Vlasiator and use it for scientific investigations. The work was supported by Academy of Finland grants: the Finnish Center of Excellence in Research of Sustainable Space grant number 312351, grant number 309937, 322544, 328893, 339756, and 338629. The work was partially funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101004131.

References

- Abdo, A. A., Ackermann, M., Ajello, M., Baldini, L., Ballet, J., Barbiellini, G., et al. (2010). Gamma-ray emission from the shell of supernova remnant W44 revealed by the Fermi LAT. *Science*, *327*, 1103–1106. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1182787>
- Battarbee, M., Ganse, U., Pfau-Kempf, Y., Turc, L., Brito, T., Grandin, M., et al. (2020). Non-locality of earth's quasi-parallel bow shock: Injection of thermal protons in a hybrid-Vlasov simulation. *Annales Geophysicae*, *38*(3), 625–643. <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-38-625-2020>
- Bell, A. R. (1978). The acceleration of cosmic rays in shock fronts. I. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, *182*, 147–156. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/182.2.147>
- Bell, A. R. (2004). Turbulent amplification of magnetic field and diffusive shock acceleration of cosmic rays. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, *353*(2), 550–558. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2004.08097.x>
- Burch, J. L., Moore, T. E., Torbert, R. B., & Giles, B. L. (2016). Magnetospheric multiscale overview and science objectives. *Space Science Reviews*, *199*, 5–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-015-0164-9>
- Burgess, D. (1989). Cyclic behavior at quasi-parallel collisionless shocks. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *16*(5), 345–348. <https://doi.org/10.1029/GL016i005p00345>
- Burgess, D. (1995). Foreshock-shock interaction at collisionless quasi-parallel shocks. *Advances in Space Research*, *15*(8–9), 159–169. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177\(94\)00098-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177(94)00098-L)
- Caprioli, D., Pop, A.-R., & Spitkovsky, A. (2015). Simulations and theory of ion injection at non-relativistic collisionless shocks. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, *798*, L28. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/798/2/L28>
- Chen, L.-J., Wang, S., Ng, J., Bessho, N., Tang, J.-M., Fung, S. F., et al. (2021). Solitary magnetic structures at quasi-parallel collisionless shocks: Formation. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *48*(1), e90800. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL090800>
- Farris, M. H., Petrinec, S. M., & Russell, C. T. (1991). The thickness of the magnetosheath - Constraints on the polytropic index. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *18*, 1821–1824. <https://doi.org/10.1029/91GL02090>
- Giacalone, J., Schwartz, S. J., & Burgess, D. (1993). Observations of suprathermal ions in association with SLAMS. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *20*, 149–152. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93GL00067>
- Greenstadt, E. W. (1985). Oblique, parallel, and quasi-parallel morphology of collisionless shocks. In B. T. Tsurutani & R. G. Stone (Eds.), *Collisionless Shocks in the Heliosphere: Reviews of Current Research. American Geophysical Union Geophysical Monograph Series* (Vol. 35, pp. 169–184). <https://doi.org/10.1029/GM035p0169>
- Hao, Y., Gao, X., Lu, Q., Huang, C., Wang, R., & Wang, S. (2017). Reformation of rippled quasi-parallel shocks: 2-d hybrid simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *122*(6), 6385–6396. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017ja024234>
- Hao, Y., Lu, Q., Gao, X., & Wang, S. (2016). Ion dynamics at a rippled quasi-parallel shock: 2d hybrid simulations. *The Astrophysical Journal*, *823*(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637x/823/1/7>
- King, J. H., & Papitashvili, N. E. (2005). Solar wind spatial scales in and comparisons of hourly Wind and ACE plasma and magnetic field data. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *110*, A02104. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JA010649>
- Lepping, R. P., Acuña, M. H., Burlaga, L. F., Farrell, W. M., Slavin, J. A., Schatten, K. H., et al. (1995). The wind magnetic field investigation. *Space Science Reviews*, *71*(1–4), 207–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00751330>
- Liu, T. Z., Hao, Y., Wilson, L. B., Turner, D. L., & Zhang, H. (2021). Magnetospheric multiscale observations of Earth's oblique bow shock reformation by foreshock ultralow-frequency waves. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *48*(2), e91184. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091184>
- Lucek, E. A., Horbury, T. S., Dandouras, I., & Rème, H. (2008). Cluster observations of the Earth's quasi-parallel bow shock. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *113*(A7), A07S02. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JA012756>
- Madanian, H., Desai, M. I., Schwartz, S. J., Wilson, I. L. B., Fuselier, S. A., Burch, J. L., et al. (2021). The dynamics of a high Mach number quasi-perpendicular shock: MMS observations. *The Astrophysical Journal*, *908*(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abc88>
- Maksimovic, M., Bale, S. D., Horbury, T. S., & André, M. (2003). Bow shock motions observed with CLUSTER. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *30*, 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002GL016761>

- Ogilvie, K. W., Chornay, D. J., Fritzenreiter, R. J., Hunsaker, F., Keller, J., Lobell, J., et al. (1995). SWE, a comprehensive plasma instrument for the wind spacecraft. *Space Science Reviews*, 71, 55–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00751326>
- Palmroth, M., Ganse, U., Pfau-Kempf, Y., Battarbee, M., Turc, L., Brito, T., et al. (2018). Vlasov methods in space physics and astrophysics. *Living Reviews in Computational Astrophysics*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41115-018-0003-2>
- Pfau-Kempf, Y., von Alfthan, S., Sandroos, A., Ganse, U., Koskela, T., Battarbee, M., & Alho, M. (2021). *fmihipc/vlasiator: Vlasiator 5.1. Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4719554>
- Pollock, C., Moore, T., Jacques, A., Burch, J., Gliese, U., Saito, Y., et al. (2016). Fast plasma investigation for magnetospheric multiscale. *Space Science Reviews*, 199, 331–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-016-0245-4>
- Russell, C. T., Anderson, B. J., Baumjohann, W., Bromund, K. R., Dearborn, D., Fischer, D., et al. (2016). The magnetospheric multiscale magnetometers. *Space Science Reviews*, 199, 189–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-014-0057-3>
- Scholer, M. (1993). Upstream waves, shocklets, short large-amplitude magnetic structures and the cyclic behavior of oblique quasi-parallel collisionless shocks. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 98(A1), 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.1029/92JA01875>
- Scholer, M., Kucharek, H., & Shinohara, I. (2003). Short large-amplitude magnetic structures and whistler wave precursors in a full-particle quasi-parallel shock simulation. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 108(A7), 1273. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JA009820>
- Schwartz, S. J. (1998). Shock and discontinuity normals, Mach numbers, and related parameters. *ISSI Scientific Reports Series*, 1, 249–270. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3052576>
- Schwartz, S. J., & Burgess, D. (1991). Quasi-parallel shocks - A patchwork of three-dimensional structures. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 18, 373–376. <https://doi.org/10.1029/91GL00138>
- Schwartz, S. J., Burgess, D., Wilkinson, W. P., Kessel, R. L., Dunlop, M., & Luehr, H. (1992). Observations of short large-amplitude magnetic structures at a quasi-parallel shock. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 97(A4), 4209–4227. <https://doi.org/10.1029/91JA02581>
- Schopke, N., Paschmann, G., Bame, S. J., Gosling, J. T., & Russell, C. T. (1983). Evolution of ion distributions across the nearly perpendicular bow shock: Specularly and non-specularly reflected-gyrating ions. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 88(A8), 6121–6136. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JA088iA08p06121>
- Sulaiman, A. H., Masters, A., Dougherty, M. K., Burgess, D., Fujimoto, M., & Hospodarsky, G. B. (2015). Quasiperpendicular high Mach number shocks. *Physical Review Letters*, 115(12), 125001. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.115.125001>
- Thomas, V. A., Winske, D., & Omid, N. (1990). Re-forming supercritical quasi-parallel shocks 1. One- and two-dimensional simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 95(A11), 18809–18819. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JA095iA11p18809>
- Thomsen, M. F., Gosling, J. T., & Russell, C. T. (1988). ISEE studies of the quasi-parallel bow shock. *Advances in Space Research*, 8(9–10), 175–178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177\(88\)90129-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177(88)90129-9)
- Tsoubouchi, K., & Lembège, B. (2004). Full particle simulations of short large-amplitude magnetic structures (SLAMS) in quasi-parallel shocks. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 109(A2), A02114. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2003JA010014>
- Turner, D. L., Wilson, I., L. B., Goodrich, K. A., Madanian, H., Schwartz, S. J., Liu, T. Z., et al. (2021). Direct multipoint observations capturing the reformation of a supercritical fast magnetosonic shock. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 911(2), L31. <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/abec78>
- Vogt, J., Haaland, S., & Paschmann, G. (2011). Accuracy of multi-point boundary crossing time analysis. *Annales Geophysicae*, 29(12), 2239–2252. <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-29-2239-2011>
- von Alfthan, S., Pokhotelov, D., Kempf, Y., Hoilijoki, S., Honkonen, I., Sandroos, A., & Palmroth, M. (2014). Vlasiator: First global hybrid-Vlasov simulations of Earth's foreshock and magnetosheath. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 120, 24–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2014.08.012>
- Winske, D., & Quest, K. B. (1988). Magnetic field and density fluctuations at perpendicular supercritical collisionless shocks. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 93, 9681–9693. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JA093iA09p09681>
- Yang, Z., Liu, Y. D., Johlander, A., Parks, G. K., Lavraud, B., Lee, E., et al. (2020). MMS direct observations of kinetic-scale shock self-reformation. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 901(1), L6. <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/abb3ff>